

How insurance status, audits, and fines affect physicians' treatment patterns: A systematic experimental analysis

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ABSTRACT

Background: When accessing and utilising health care, patients face several information asymmetries. For example, patients without a diagnosis cannot specifically search for a treatment of their symptoms to compare treatment costs ex-ante and cannot evaluate the quality of the treatment ex-post. Therefore, health care fulfils the properties of a credence good, a type of good with qualities that cannot be observed by the consumer after purchase. These properties make it difficult for the consumer to assess the utility of a credence good. It furthermore creates incentives for sellers to exploit their information advantage. In health care, this situation can lead to a mismatch between the severity of a condition and the recommended treatment, resulting in inefficiencies such as under/overtreatment and the possibility of overcharging. This study investigates the effects of the insurance status (private/social health insurance), capacity constraints, audits of the providers, as well as fines on the level of under/overtreatment and overcharging.

Methods: The effect of the different conditions on the treatment allocations for hypothetical patients with low and high severity conditions will be investigated in a laboratory experiment, using a sample of medical and economics students. Participants can choose to treat or under/overtreat a patient that requires either a simple or complex intervention. In a second step, participants can charge for the performed treatment or overcharge patients. The effect of different audit probabilities and fines levels will be tested between subjects while the effect of capacity constraints and the insurance status will be tested within subjects. We expect to have results of the full sample with $N \approx 300$ ready by March to be able to present results for all conditions.

Results: Theoretical predictions based on the literature suggest that privately insured patients (fee for service) are more likely to be overtreated than patients with social health insurance (capitation). Under capacity constraints the risk of undertreatment increases, while increasing audit probabilities and fines are expected to reduce the level of mismatches between severity and treatments. Preliminary results from a pilot support these predictions. We furthermore expect to find lower levels of mismatches among medical students, possibly due to higher levels of altruism.

Conclusion: Information asymmetries between physicians and patients combined with the market incentives of the payment system can lead to suboptimal treatment and reimbursement decisions. This paper will show if different payment mechanisms (insurance status), capacity constraints and audits of the providers will affect the degree of mismatches between the required and the recommended treatments.